

Studies on the Suppression of Polarographic Maximum of Nitrobenzene by Ionic and Non-ionic Surfactants vis-a-vis their Influence on the Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction

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Manuscript received 30 September 1977, revised 9 January 1978,
accepted 22 February 1978

LAL and Srivastava¹ have studied the suppression of polarographic maximum of nitrobenzene by some ionic and non-ionic surfactants with a view to compare their relative efficacies for quenching the maximum to half of the original value. In the present paper an attempt has been made to study the kinetics of the electrode reaction of nitrobenzene as a function of concentration of some more ionic and non-ionic surfactants from the stage where maximum just disappears. This provides a better opportunity for comparing the efficacy of different surfactants in suppressing the maximum.

Experimental

All the chemical used were of BDH Analar grade. The surfactants used were: Lauryl pyridinium chloride (LPC), Cetyl pyridinium chloride (CPC), Cetyl dimethylbenzyl ammonium chloride (CDBAC), Sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), Dodecylbenzene sulphonate (DBS), Dioctyl sodium sulphosuccinate (DSSS), Triton X-100, 2-ethoxy ethanol, Ethylidigol and Gelatin.

A manual polarograph (Toshniwal, CLO2) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal, PL50) was used. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using McIlvaine buffer (pH 7). The purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.). The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M KCl, open circuit).

$$h_{\text{corr}} = 73.12 \text{ cm}; t = 3.60 \text{ sec};$$

$$m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.672 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}$$

The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction process was determined by millicoulometric method of Devries and Kroon² using a mercury pool cathode. This gave the value of n equal to 4 at pH 7. Having known the value of n , Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of D , the diffusion coefficient of nitrobenzene at various concentrations of the surfactants.

Results and Discussion

Nitrobenzene under the chosen experimental conditions yields a negative maximum at -0.70V (S.C.E.). The values of polarographic characteristics

of nitrobenzene in the presence of minimum amount of each surfactant needed to suppress the maximum have been summarised in Table 1. Representative Fig. 1. depicts the effect of increasing amounts of LPC on current-voltage curves. After the removal of the maximum the limiting current has been found to be diffusion controlled in each case as evidenced by the linearity of i_d vs $\sqrt{h}$ plots.

Fig. 1 C-V curves of Nitrobenzene in the presence of different concentrations of LPC.

[LPC] 1. 0.0%, 2. $8.0 \times 10^{-11}\%$, 3. $1.6 \times 10^{-10}\%$,
4. $2.4 \times 10^{-10}\%$, 5. $3.2 \times 10^{-10}\%$,
6. $4.0 \times 10^{-10}\%$, 7. $8.0 \times 10^{-10}\%$.

On applying various tests of irreversibility³⁻⁶ it has been found that the reduction of nitrobenzene at d.m.e. is totally irreversible. The potential dependent rate constant ($k_{t,h}$) for the electrode reaction has been calculated by Koutecky's method⁷. Having calculated $k_{t,h}$ at various stages of a wave αn_a values were calculated from the slope of $\log k_{t,h}$ vs $E_{d.o.}$ plots⁸ and are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1.—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF NITROBENZENE (25% ETHANOLIC SOLUTION) IN MCILVAINE BUFFER (pH 7)
[Nitrobenzene] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Surfactant used	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V S.C.E.	Slope mV	αn_a
Cationic				
LPC ($3.2 \times 10^{-10}\%$)	14.72	0.62	68	0.76
CPC ($2.8 \times 10^{-10}\%$)	14.82	0.63	71	0.81
CDBAC ($1.2 \times 10^{-10}\%$)	15.25	0.60	59	0.92
Anionic				
SLS ($3.2 \times 10^{-10}\%$)	15.96	0.64	74	0.73
DBS ($1.6 \times 10^{-10}\%$)	14.01	0.62	69	0.78
DSSS ($2.4 \times 10^{-10}\%$)	14.72	0.64	76	0.73
Non-ionic				
Gelatin ($4.0 \times 10^{-5}\%$)	16.32	0.60	100	0.60
Triton X-100 ($1.6 \times 10^{-5}\%$)	15.08	0.62	68	0.78
2-Ethoxy ethanol ($1.6 \times 10^{-5}\%$)	16.85	0.62	84	0.73
Ethylidigol ($1.6 \times 10^{-5}\%$)	15.43	0.62	75	0.75

At pH 7 the reduction of nitrobenzene at d.m.e. takes place in a 4-electron step. This is in conformity with the earlier investigations⁹⁻¹¹. The αn_a values listed in Table 1 have been calculated at the surfactant concentration where maximum is just suppressed. Since n_a has been shown¹² to be equal to 2, it becomes possible to estimate the

corresponding values of α . It is well known^{1,2} that the presence of surfactants affects the kinetics of electrode processes and consequently αn_a (and hence α) values are also affected. Recently, Singh et al^{1,2} while studying the suppression of Ni(II) maxima have compared the efficacies of the suppressors in terms of αn_a values at the concentrations where maximum is just suppressed. The order of αn_a values (which should also be the order of α -values) at any comparative situation for different surfactants should signify the extent to which the addition of ionic and non-ionic surfactants pushes the electrode reaction of nitrobenzene towards irreversibility. In the present study this push towards irreversibility at the point of just suppression is in the following order :

Cationic : LPC > CPC > CDBAC

Anionic : DSSS > SLS > DBS

Non-ionic : Gelatin > 2-ethoxy ethanol > ethyldigol > Triton X-100. Thus CDBAC, DBS and Triton X-100 eliminate the polarographic maximum with least influence on the kinetics of electron transfer.

The effect of increasing concentration of the surfactants beyond the stage of just suppression on αn_a values has also been investigated and it has been observed that a decrease in the values of αn_a takes place. From this it is inferred^{1,5-1,7} that the electrode reaction of nitrobenzene becomes more irreversible at higher concentrations of the surfactants.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to the Principal, Agra College, Agra for providing necessary facilities and to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for granting a Junior Research Fellowship to one of the authors (R.R.).

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A Note on General Mathematical Expression for Stress-Strain Behaviour and Molecular Structure

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Manuscript received 16 July 1977, revised 12 January 1978,

accepted 26 April 1978

FROM statistical considerations, by a rigorous but straightforward mathematical treatment we obtained the following expression for the energy stored, $\Delta W^{(def)}$, due to deformation of a rubber-elastic polymer network at constant temperature T ,

$$\Delta W^{(def)} = nkT[(3/2)(L/nl)^2(\alpha_x^2 + \alpha_y^2 + \alpha_z^2 - 3) + (9/20)(L/nl)^4(\alpha_x^4 + \alpha_y^4 + \alpha_z^4 - 3) + (99/350)(L/nl)^6(\alpha_x^6 + \alpha_y^6 + \alpha_z^6 - 3) + \dots] - KT \ln \alpha_x \alpha_y \alpha_z = \dots \quad (1)$$

For the last term of above equation, i.e., $KT \ln \alpha_x \alpha_y \alpha_z$ at present we assumed Flory's approach¹.

Where

n = number of effective flexible links in the polymer chain between adjacent crosslinks.

l = length of each flexible link.

k = Boltzmann constant.

T = absolute temperature.

L = average length per chain, in each of x , y and z directions.

and α_x , α_y and α_z are factors by which L is deformed in x , y and z directions. That is in x direction L changes to $L \alpha_x$ in y direction to $L \alpha_y$ and in z direction to $L \alpha_z$.

For elongation of a sample by a factor of L at constant volume^{6,7} the tensile force, τ , per initial cross-sectional unit area as :

$$\tau = \frac{kT}{L^2 l} \left[\alpha^{-1} \left(\frac{L\alpha}{nl} \right) - \alpha^{-\frac{3}{2}} \alpha^{-1} \left(\frac{L\alpha^{-\frac{1}{2}}}{nl} \right) \right] \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\text{or } \tau = (kT/L^2 l) [3(L/nl)(\alpha - 1/\alpha^3)$$

$$+ (9/5)(L/nl)^3 \left(\alpha^3 - \frac{1}{\alpha^3} \right)$$

$$+ (297/175)(L/nl)^5 \left(\alpha^5 - \frac{1}{\alpha^5} \right) + \dots] \dots \quad (3)$$

where α^{-1} denotes inverse Langevin function.

It is obvious that the first term of the right-hand